

THE INTERACTION BETWEEN POTASSIUM META-PERIODATE AND THE SOLUBLE SALTS OF METALS OF ALKALINE EARTHS.

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On boiling a solution of potassium metaperiodate, KIO_4 , with the soluble salts of the alkaline earths, the corresponding dimesoperiodates in hydrated form are precipitated. These are octahydrated calcium dimesoperiodate, $Ca_2I_2O_8 \cdot 8H_2O$, octahydrated strontium dimesoperiodate, $Sr_2I_2O_8 \cdot 8H_2O$ and tetrahydrated barium dimesoperiodate, $Ba_2I_2O_8 \cdot 4H_2O$.

Bahl and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 375) obtained the mesoperiodates of the rare earths by boiling disodium paraperiodate $Na_2H_3IO_6$ with an excess of soluble salts of the corresponding rare earths. Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1771) studied the reaction of the same sodium salt with the soluble salts of the metals of the alkaline earths. Their results show that no definite strontium compound is formed, while calcium yields tetrahydrated calcium dimesoperiodate, $Ca_2I_2O_8 \cdot 4H_2O$, and the barium salt $2 \cdot 3BaO \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$.

In the present work the interaction between potassium metaperiodate, KIO_4 (obtained by passing chlorine gas through a boiling solution of potassium hydroxide in the presence of iodine) and an excess of the soluble salts of the alkaline earth, has been investigated. It is found that calcium, strontium and barium form octahydrated calcium dimesoperiodate, $Ca_2I_2O_8 \cdot 8H_2O$, octahydrated strontium dimesoperiodate, $Sr_2I_2O_8 \cdot 8H_2O$, and tetrahydrated barium dimesoperiodate, $Ba_2I_2O_8 \cdot 4H_2O$ respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A hot solution of potassium metaperiodate, KIO_4 , was added to a boiling solution of the chlorides of the corresponding alkaline earth. A white precipitate was formed in each case. For the precipitate of strontium salt prolonged heating was found necessary. The precipitates were filtered, washed, dried in an electric air oven at 40° and then analysed.

Alkaline earth was determined as the corresponding sulphate. Iodine and the available oxygen were estimated by the methods adopted by Partington and Bahl (*loc. cit.*).

*Analytical Results.**Calcium salt, Ca₂I₂O₉, 8H₂O.*

Sample	Calcium.		Iodine.		Available oxygen.	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	12.20%	12.88%	41.11%	40.90%	17.86%	18.03%
2.	12.40		41.11		17.90	
3.	12.20		41.20		17.93	

Strontium salt, Sr₂I₂O₉, 8H₂O.

1.	25.09	24.43	34.89	35.40	15.50	15.60
2.	24.80		35.00		15.50	
3.	24.84		35.14		15.50	

Barium salt, Ba₂I₂O₉, 4H₂O.

1.	36.22	37.88	34.90	34.10	15.20	15.30
2.	36.40		34.65		15.20	
3.	36.24		34.70		15.20	

From the above it appears that it is not necessary that the same kind of periodate should be formed by double decomposition. Thus potassium metaperiodate, KIO₄, and disodium paraperiodate, Na₂H₃IO₆, on boiling with the soluble salts of alkaline earth do not form the corresponding periodates but they yield dimesoperiodates.

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